

VILNIUS ART ACADEMY

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

In Lithuania, the *Labour Code*¹ (2016) and the *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men*² (last amended in 2017) are the key legislation regulating how universities and research organisations address the issues of gender-based violence (GBV) at work and in education. The amended *Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men* obliges higher education and research institutions to ensure equal rights for women and men and to undertake measures to stop any sexual harassment and protect students and staff in these institutions (2017, Art. 5 para. 5).

Universities have developed policies on antidiscrimination, equal opportunities, and diversity and have integrated gender as a category on which grounds discrimination, harassment, and sexual harassment is prohibited. Prevention and protection against sexual harassment are often the only types of action which the specific policies have been adopted. Some universities developed these policies after the Conference of University Rectors adopted in 2020 the Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidences (hereinafter the Guidelines).³ All universities have integrated the Recommendations on the Approval, Embedding, and Monitoring of Academic Ethics Codes by Research and Higher Education Institutions⁴ (hereinafter the Recommendations) approved by the Ombudsperson for Academic Ethics and Procedures. The Recommendations do not specifically mention GBV in universities, but they refer to integrity, justice, trust, equality, and responsibility as the main principles of academic ethics.

According to data from 2021, there are 11 public and four private universities in Lithuania. Six public and one private university have adopted policy documents on equal opportunities including gender equality and four public universities have adopted Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

¹ Labour Code, No. XII-260 (2016, last amended 2021). <https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/f6d686707e7011e6b969d7ae07280e89>.

² Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men, No. XII-2767 (2016, last amended 2017). <https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/d6ed8e50a74a11e68987e8320e9a5185>.

³ The Conference of Universities' Rectors (2020). Guidelines for the Prevention of Sexual Harassment and Investigation of Its Incidence. https://lurk.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/07/Seksualinio-priekabiavimo-prevencijos-ir-atvej%C5%B3-nagrin%C4%97jimo-gair%C4%97s-2020m-be-nuorod%C5%B3_T.pdf.

⁴ Rekomendacijos mokslo ir studijų institucijų akademinės etikos kodeksų priėmimo, įgyvendinimo ir priežiūros rekomendacijos, V-16, (2015, last amendment 2020, V-38). <https://etikostarnyba.lt/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/V-38.pdf>

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

Vilnius Art Academy (VAA) has a set of two general policies that address GBV. The main policy document is the Equal Opportunity Policy and Regulations to Implement the Prevention of Sexual Harassment at Vilnius Academy of Arts (hereinafter the Policy). It provides a broader definition of sexual harassment than the definition given in the Act on Equal Opportunities for Women and Men. The Policy identifies the conditions and circumstances in which sexual harassment occurs: by demonstrating dominant status such as hierarchical relations and unequal status in the organisation; power relations to decide (for example, power to decide about the grade, assessment of professional achievements or promotion); power based on coercion (for example, conduct that causes psychological and physical threat) or sexual harassment that occurs between equals in their professional status. The document also provides the procedure to notify and/or complain about experienced discrimination or sexual harassment, the procedure and timeframe for investigation of the complaint, the mechanism of applied sanctions for a perpetrator and opportunities to get counselling without a formal complaint.

VAA adopted the Action Plan to Implement Equality at Vilnius Academy of Arts (hereinafter called the Action Plan), which indicates several measures for the prevention of sexual harassment. The electronic portal [Reporting on Sexual Harassment](#) provides instructions on submitting anonymised complaints about discrimination and/or sexual harassment that inform people that they can submit information about an incident along with their e-mail contact information to one of the persons authorised to deal with such issues: the head of the Department of Studies' Quality, a psychologist, the dean of the faculty, and the chairperson of the Senate Ethics Committee.

URLs

- › The Policy and the Action Plan can be found here: <https://www.vda.lt/lt/apie-vda/etika>

Entry into force: Both documents were adopted on 21 December 2020.

TRAINING

The Policy refers to trainings as part of the preventive measures. Trainings were planned for all staff but have not yet been implemented due to the COVID-19 lockdown. Training will be resumed when the situation changes. The Action Plan states that since 2021 there has been a requirement to inform all employees, including newcomers, about the policies of equal opportunities and the prevention of sexual harassment. The plan is that the majority of staff will have to pass e-training courses on discrimination and sexual harassment, how to identify these behaviours, and what to do about them. The document stipulates that the administration of VAA and the Equal Opportunities Group are responsible for implementing these actions.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

None. The institution will support individual interest in GBV on the part of a student or member of the academic staff if they initiate research on or include GBV in their final work. But on the institutional level there is no separate discipline or topic devoted to GBV in any study programmes.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The two policies combined address the following **five** forms of GBV: sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender-based harassment, stalking, and online violence. The Action Plan focuses only on sexual harassment while the Policy addresses all of the above.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The two policies combined cover the following **5Ps**: prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and policy. The main document, the Equal Opportunity Policy and Regulations to Implement the Prevention of Sexual Harassment at Vilnius Academy of Arts, covers all 5Ps, while the Action Plan addresses prevention and protection.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Target groups: Both documents address academic and non-academic staff and students.

Specific vulnerable groups

None.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Bystanders addressed: Yes. In the section 'Prevention against Discrimination and Sexual Harassment', the Policy includes a measure that is designed to encourage people to not be bystanders and indifferently observe violations but to take an active stance and try to stop such behaviour.

Role of perpetrators addressed: Yes. The Policy specifies that a perpetrator should be informed about the allegation against him/her/them and have the same rights as a victim to participate in and/or withdraw from the process of investigation and get support in terms of representation and legal support, and that they can ask for a member of the investigation commission to be replaced. It is also indicated that sanctions can be applied to a perpetrator.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: No.

Evaluation: No.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

Yes. The Policy sets out a step-by-step institutional procedure for reporting and investigation. There is **one procedure for all**.

The policy defines: Who to contact, how to report, the investigation procedure, responsible persons or units, and available sanctions.

Who to contact: The policy document indicates that complaints or requests for consultation on issues relating to sexual harassment or discrimination can be submitted to any of the persons listed in the document: the person indicated as responsible for such issues, psychologists, the dean or vice-dean, and the VAA Ethics Committee or its chair. Complaints may be submitted in written or oral form or by e-mail. There is an electronic portal, '[Reporting on Sexual Harassment](#)', through which it is possible to submit anonymised complaints about discrimination and/or sexual harassment.

Unit responsible for investigating cases: When one of the authorised persons listed above receives a complaint, they should pass the complaint on to the Ethics Committee for further investigation.

Investigation procedure: Only the Ethics Committee can initiate an investigation by collecting evidence from a victim, the alleged perpetrator, and witnesses. The following criteria apply for

identifying harassment: the nature of the incident, its intensity, when it happened, in what locations, in what context, and how long it lasted.

Investigation timeline: The timeline for the investigation is two months starting from the day on which a complaint is received. If the case is complicated, the investigation can be prolonged or postponed. The incidents and violations on which a complaint is filed should not have occurred more than four years prior to a complaint.

Sanctions: Though sanctions for violations are not listed, the procedure for sanctioning is indicated. If a violation is proved, the Rector of the VAA makes a decision on sanctions based on the decision of the Ethics Committee. The decision on disciplinary measures will be based on the provisions in the Labour Code and internal legal provisions (warnings, disciplinary or other sanctions). If the Rector is found guilty of sexual harassment or discrimination, then the decision on disciplinary measures will be made by the Council of the Academy.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

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